

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: LLM

COURSE CODE: ACA-401

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author did use Zotero to insert references
The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)
The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-13)
3. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2021, 14-16)
4. What is a Style Guide, and Why Would I Need One? (EUCLID 2021, 24-26)
5. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 27-34)
6. Sample Corrections to Papers (EUCLID 2021, 37-43)
7. CMS Crib Sheet (EUCLID 2021, 44-55)

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GUIDELINES FOR WRITING ACADEMIC PAPERS

1) INTRODUCTION

One may assume that one can write an academic paper in English, where one is born, raised, and educated in a country whose official language is English. I was therefore startled when I enrolled for the first ACA-401, whose period one was about the basics of essay writing. Being a legal practitioner in a corporate entity involves a lot of writing. Papers, notices, and letters are reviewed every day, not to mention the drafting of pleadings. At undergraduate school, the coursework came with instruction on the font style and size to use. We were given a stern warning against plagiarism, with a lecturer stating that they had the software to check for plagiarism. The assumption was that we all knew how to write and how to speak English. With this background, I assumed that the course I had enrolled for would begin with an "Introduction to International Law" and that I would quickly maneuver the

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Master's degree. I would have never imagined that there is a process to writing an academic paper save for writing out an answer for the question.

The first chapter of ACA-401 period one (1) spells out the basics of essay writing. This process does not begin and end with writing the paper. Instead, it involves the

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construction of an initial essay plan, reading and organizing one's research and ideas into an answer. (EUCLID 2021, 3-4).

While it may not be the case in academic writing, it is common to go through life hurriedly and live each day as it comes. One may not take time to plan carefully, thoroughly research and execute an assignment. It may also be true in instances where one's line of work involves repeated actions and responses. The first chapter of ACA 401 period one, I emphasizes carefully planning an academic essay. One ought to think of the planning as part of the writing, not separate from the writing process. (Warburton 2006, 8-9). Therefore, a keen student must take time to do the necessary preparations to write an excellent paper. The planning includes putting the relevant sources of information together and studying them for their relevance in answering whichever question the student seeks to answer. The student must then decide on what information to use in drafting their essay.

Reading the course material, which underscores the importance of timely planning in academic writing, I have realized that I must not hurry through the course and its requirements. I must give thought to all the course material that I read in preparation for each paper that I will write. I also realize that giving careful thought to the source of information and planning to write instead of allowing the ideas to flow as I write will make a difference in the outcome of my essay and my general understanding of the course I am undertaking.

2) PLAGIARISM

As I read the chapter on plagiarism, I wondered whether it is the norm to think of the morality of one's every action or whether one thinks of the consequence of their actions retrospectively, if at all. The adage "give credit where it is due" came to mind as I read on further. Do students eager to broaden their career prospects through completing a master's program at the earliest give thought to what the academician who worked long and hard to put together the resources being used must have gone through? Is it entirely unethical or even inconsequential when the student writes the paper while collecting information from various sources and paraphrasing it for their purposes? After all, the concept may not be entirely new. One may also argue that the author's work influenced their thought process. How then is one supposed to rewrite it? (Green 2002, 182)

The chapter on plagiarism emphasizes that over and above the relevance of one's academic pursuits, one must seriously consider the consequences of one's actions during the study. I must at all times be aware of the morality of my every action, more specifically while writing academic papers, to give credit where it is due.

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3) SOME RULES OF THE THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

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The rules of the thumb mentioned in chapter three of ACA-401 Period (one) 1 lead one to the realization that a student may quickly start writing a paper without an actual plan on the direction it will take and the question it seeks to answer. One must get a thesis if one does not already have one (EUCLID 2021, 14). The rules of the thumb tie in with the concept of planning as they too are essential tools with which a student can successfully build the skill of academic writing.

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From the reading in this chapter, I noted that I must read, and conceptualize the arguments fronted in the material, understand the author's view(s) and build on the understanding as I write the essay. In effect, one must seek first to understand before settling to write an academic paper. This ties in with the notion that one must take the views one is discussing seriously. To treat a subject with the seriousness it deserves requires that one takes time to plan an appropriate response to a question, which in turn requires that one gains an in-depth understanding of a concept before arguing for or against the author of the material referred to in the essay.

4) WHAT IS A STYLE GUIDE, AND WHY WOULD I NEED ONE?

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I belong to a book club that meets every so often to discuss a book chosen by one of the book club members and read by all the members. More often than not, a writer's style is a subject of discussion. During the literature classes in high school, the teacher often called for an analysis of the author's style and language, usually associated with the book's setting- both geographical and in terms of time. I must say that while I have read literary works of a fictional nature, I had never given much thought to 'a style guide' as a concept.

Chapter five of the course pack was an entirely new concept for me. As I read further, I realized that 'style' was something I had possibly observed but never known to be a subject or to have a name. What makes a style guide important is the need for consistency (EUCLID 2021, 24). For an online program such as this one, the instructor will have several papers to read through. The unique background, experience, and circumstance of each student will affect their writing. Without compliance with the style guide, the perusal of the papers submitted will be an uphill task for the instructor. Similarly, for the student, the documents authored meet the institution's standard as far as the style is concerned and allow for uniformity which is an essential part of any institution's reputation and identity.

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5) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

The introduction to chapter six of the coursepack mentions reasons why American English is currently the dominant influence on "world English." One of the reasons listed is the appeal of American pop culture on language and habits. While pop culture is widely consumed and has been influential on the public (consumers) perception and opinions on social realities (Asimow 2006, 668), one may not be aware of its influence on one's language. It is a commonplace to hear a person imitating another's accent, especially where one has been abroad. The interference of the mother tongue has also affected spoken English here in Uganda.

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The reading made me stop to think about what affects the English I speak and write and to question what effect my choice of entertainment and mainstream media has on English as I have always known it. While my society may use British and American English interchangeably, the local dialects have affected the language. This chapter made me ask myself which English I have been speaking and writing and whether or not it is British, American, Ugandan English, or all three, depending on the circumstances.

6) SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

Chapter seven of the course pack on sample corrections to papers is very pertinent. It enabled me to put into context what I had read in the previous chapters. I read some paragraphs over and over again in a bid to understand what needed correction and why. Several times, I caught myself wondering where the error was.

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Like, the previous chapter's reading on the differences between American and British English, this chapter underscores the importance of indicating the choice of English used in the papers I write. More importantly, I have to be more accommodative when reading any piece of writing because, as I now realize, the factors influencing one's English are more than I know.

7) CONCLUSION

For one whose educational background and current situation in the workplace have not dictated the way documents are written to the detail entailed in the course pack for ACA- 401 period one, it might seem a bit overwhelming and even somewhat daunting. Chapter eight on the CMS Crib sheet is critical because it is the guidance a student needs as they embark on drafting papers as they undertake their studies. Several times in the last week one week, I caught myself doubting whether or not I would learn what is required and how long it would take before a paper I author meets the standard required of a Master's student.

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By the end of my reading, I fully appreciated how important it is to harness my writing skills before delving into the subject course. I also realize that the fundamentals of academic writing are a priority if one is to navigate the course successfully.

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